

ON THE ELASTIC MODULI OF THERMOPLASTICS (PEEK) REINFORCED BY SHORT FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

Short glass and carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites have been prepared by injection molding and then microscopically characterized. Their Young Moduli have been obtained by two different methods : a classical unidirectional tensile test and an immersion ultrasonic technique. Results are compared and discussed in the context offered by the theory of reinforcement of Kelly-Tyson, and the original processing and microstructural characteristics of short fibre reinforced thermoplastic systems.

1.- INTRODUCTION

Short fibre reinforced thermoplastics (SFRT) are intermediate materials between unreinforced polymers and classical long fibre composites. Comparing the properties of SFRT with those of unreinforced polymers is commonly observed that the incorporation of chopped fibres in a thermoplastic matrix produces significant improvements in stiffness and strength, though there is often a marked reduction in ductility. On the other hand, the fact that short fibre reinforced thermoplastics consist of chopped and often disoriented fibres, makes them not to be able to compete in stiffness and strength with the classical unidirectional long fibre composites. These disadvantages, however, are compensated by the fact that they can be manufactured by usual processing methods for thermoplastics such as extrusion and injection molding.

Microstructure of a SFRT is set up during the manufacturing step and is a key factor to understand mechanical properties of the final molded part. This paper intends to be a contribution to the understanding of SFRT with PEEK as thermoplastic matrix. Second, the ultrasonic investigation for mechanical characterization of this kind of materials is tested.

2.- MATERIALS AND PROCESSING

Poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK) is a high temperature resistant semicrystalline thermoplastic of excellent mechanical properties and great potential as matrix material for high performance composites. The high performance of PEEK is attributed to its highly aromatized ether linked chemical structure ¹ :

In this work, the commercial 30% by weight short glass and carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites supplied by Imperial Chemical Industries (ICI) - Victrex PEEK 450 GL 30 and Victrex PEEK 450 CA 30 respectively - were combined in appropriate proportions with unreinforced grades of the same polymer (PEEK 450 G) to obtain the following spectrum of materials with varying volume content of glass fibres (Vgf) and carbon fibres (Vcf) :

Wf (%)	Vgf (%)	Vcf (%)	PEEK/GF	PEEK/CF
0	0	0	PEEK	PEEK
10	5.4	7.4	GPEEK10	CPEEK10
20	11.3	15.3	GPEEK20	CPEEK20
30	17.9	23.1	GPEEK30	CPEEK30

Blending was carried out in a Brabender Plasticorder PLE-650 extruder machine with a screw aspect ratio L/D = 25 at 400 °C . Extruded bands of 0.5 mm depth were obtained and then palletised by milling. This material was then injection molded in a Battenfield BA230 preplasticizing injection machine at varying barrel temperatures from 370 to 390 °C depending on the material fibre content. Injection pressures and speeds were kept constant all over the range of fibre compositions and mold temperature was fixed at 165°C. In order to have all materials processed in the most similar conditions even unreinforced and 30 % reinforced materials were previously extruded. At the end of the process tensile specimens (ASTM D-638) were obtained .

3.- MECHANICAL TESTING AND ULTRASONIC CHARACTERIZATION

3.1.- A classical tensile test (ASTM D-638) was carried out at 5 mm/min and 25 °C of temperature with tensile specimens obtained by injection molding and their Young Moduli were measured from the slope of their stress-strain curves at low strains. Stress and strain measurements were based on the initial cross sectional area of the tensile specimens and the obtained values are the mean of at least six determinations.

3.2.- Shoulders of injection specimens subjected to a dispersive melting flow during the molding operation were tested by an **ultrasonic immersion method** at 25 °C of temperature and 5MHz of wave frequency. The technique used in this work is that employed by Hosten ² to identify the anisotropic behavior of composite materials. As tensile specimen's surfaces at their central parts are not wide enough to intercept completely the transducer beam, shoulder parts have been used to carry out these measurements (Figure 1). Determination of ultrasonic wave speeds in various planes of propagation have permitted the identification of the elastic constants from which Young Moduli in the direction of melting flow and two other perpendicular directions have been obtained.

Figure 1. Injection molding tensile specimen shoulder submitted to an ultrasonic beam at a θ angle of incidence.

U. T. : Ultrasonic Transmitter. U. R.: Ultrasonic Receiver.

4.- FIBRE REINFORCEMENT THEORY

The prediction of stress of a short fibre composite at one given strain can be made by a little modification in the simple law of mixtures of uniaxially aligned continuous fibre composites:

$$\sigma_c = \eta_0 \eta_1 \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (1),$$

where σ_c , σ_f and σ_m are the stress of the composite, fibre and matrix at that given strain ; V_f is the fibre volume content; η_0 and η_1 are both efficiency factors that take into account the fibre penalty in stress contribution to composite due to their misalignment and short length respectively.

Kelly and Tyson ³, accepting the assumption originally made by Cox ⁴ that stresses in a short fibre composite can be carried out by a shear transfer process at the fibre-matrix interface, introduced the concept of critical fibre length L_c . Consequently, the length necessary for the maximum stress in the fibre to reach a fibre fracture stress σ_f^u , takes the following form :

$$L_c = \frac{r \sigma_f^u}{\tau} \quad (2).$$

Here r is the radius of the fibre and τ the fibre-matrix interfacial shear strength.

For subcritical fibre of length L_i , the average stress in the fibre is given by: $\bar{\sigma}_f = \frac{L_i \tau}{2r}$

which means that $\eta_1 = \frac{L_i}{2L_c}$

For supercritical fibre of length L_j , however, the average stress is given by $\bar{\sigma}_f = \sigma_f^u (1 - \frac{\sigma_f^u r}{2L_j \tau})$, thus $\eta_1 = 1 - \frac{L_c}{2L_j}$

Bowyer and Bader ⁵, separating the respective contributions of subcritical fibres (X), supercritical fibres (Y) and matrix (Z) to the composite strength gave to the modified rule of mixtures the following form:

$$\sigma_c = \eta_0 (X+Y) + Z \quad (3)$$

where,

$$X = \sum_{L_i < L_c} \frac{L_i \tau}{2r} V_i \quad (4)$$

$$Y = \sum_{L_j > L_c} (1 - \frac{\sigma_f^u r}{2L_j \tau}) \sigma_f^u V_j \quad (5)$$

$$Z = \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (6)$$

V_i and V_j are the respective volume contents of subcritical and supercritical fibres.

This method predicts the values of L_c and the orientation efficiency factor η_0 when fibre length distributions and the σ - ϵ behavior of the fibre, matrix and composite are experimentally known. However a constant value of τ has to be assumed in the calculations and this postulation has been demonstrated not to be correct. Mittal and al ⁶ propose a linear variation of τ with σ substituting $\tau = K\sigma$ in the above mentioned equations.

At very low strains, when the effects of built up stress from fibre ends can be neglected the theory gets simplified for the elastic prediction. Therefore, Young Modulus of composite will be expressed as a single efficiency parameter dependent linear function:

$$E_c = \eta_0 E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f). \quad (7)$$

5.- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1.- Tensile Young Modulus

The effect of fibre type on elastic modulus is studied from Figure 2. This figure shows that short carbon (CF) and glass fibre (GF) reinforced PEEK composites follow a linear trend with fibre volume content. As was 'a priori' expected from higher modulus of CF, the slope of PEEK/CF systems is higher than that of PEEK/GF systems.

Figure 2. Tensile Young Modulus of PEEK/CF and PEEK/GF systems.

The theory of reinforcement presented here for short fibre reinforced composites neglects the penalty in stress contribution of fibres due to their shortness when fibres are longer than the strain developed during the tensile test. Following this assumption, fibre orientation efficiency factors (η_0) have been calculated by introducing the bibliographic values of $E_{CF} = 210$ GPa and $E_{GF} = 69$ GPa, and the experimentally determined E_m , E_f and V_f values in equation (1). Table 1 shows the orientation efficiency values of our PEEK systems and those of other thermoplastics commonly used as matrices for short glass fibre reinforced systems processed by injection molding with similar geometries. The lower values obtained in PEEK/GF in comparison with those obtained in Nylon/GF or in PP/GF systems should be explained in terms of the different rheological properties of SFRT due to the different nature of the matrix.

	η_0
GPEEK30	0.40
GPEEK10	0.48
CPEEK30	0.21
CPEEK10	0.22
Polypropylene/GF (Wf=30%) ⁷	0.53
Nylon 6,6/GF (Wf=30%) ⁵	0.57

Table 1. Comparison of fibre orientation efficiency factor in PEEK, Polypropylene, and Nylon 6,6 SFRT.

As concerns PEEK/CF, their orientation efficiency values are much lower than those of PEEK/GF. Figure 3 is the fibre length distribution histogram of CPEEK10 with a number average value of $\bar{L} = 130 \mu\text{m}$ obtained from its Gaussian decomposition curve. Similar distributions have been obtained with the rest of materials. GPEEK 30 histogram before processing gave nearly the same average length value ($\bar{L} = 209 \mu\text{m}$) and form of that published by Wu and Schultz⁸ for 450 GL 30 ($\bar{L} = 211 \mu\text{m}$). The average fibre length values of these materials are shown in table 2.

Figure 3. Fibre distribution histogram of CPEEK 10 after extrusion and injection molding operations.

	$\bar{L}_n(\mu\text{m})$	standard deviation
GPEEK 30 (granules)	209	108
CPEEK 30 (granules)	170	93
GPEEK 30 (molded part)	176	73
CPEEK 30 (molded part)	103	53
GPEEK 10 (molded part)	189	79
CPEEK 10 (molded part)	135	87

Table 2. Number average fibre length and standard deviation of composites before and after processing.

Bayley⁹ has shown that lower length values in SFRT increase the alignment of fibres in the mold filling direction. This effect together with the fact that rheological behavior of PEEK meltings with carbon and glass fibres must be different should be considered if an explanation to the low values of η_0 of CF was to be given. However, the exact origin of carbon fibres is unknown to us. This fact, considering that η_0 values are very sensitive to the theoretical value given to Young modulus of carbon fibre, make us to be cautious and not to take definitive conclusions at this point.

5.2.- Critical fibre length

Actual fibre length distributions and σ - ϵ curves have also been used to obtain fibre critical length values by the method proposed by Bowder and Bayer. The aim of their work was the prediction of the non linear part of the stress-strain curve on the hypothesis that fibres carry the external stress by shear at their ends. Fixing the η_0 values obtained previously, critical fibre length value has been calculated for GPEEK 30 and CPEEK 30 at different strains. These calculations have been carried out trying different L_c values in the equations 3, 4, 5, 6 up to the following condition was satisfied : $\frac{\sigma_c - \sigma_m(1-V_f)}{X+Y} = \eta_0$.

Table 3 shows these results. Fibre critical length increases with strain up to strain at break for both SFRT systems. Moreover the values of L_c are always higher for CPEEK 30 than for GPEEK 30. This is an evidence - to which it should be added that given by experimentally measured shorter length values obtained in CF systems- of the higher presence of subcritical fibres in carbon fibre injection moldings with regards to GF reinforced ones. Table 4 shows the values of τ and the proportionality constant K at break strain of these two mentioned systems with those given in the bibliography^{5, 7, 10} for commercial similar materials based in other thermoplastics. As can be observed shear stress in CF-PEEK interface is higher than that in GF-PEEK interface. Moreover, the results show that PEEK offers to short fibre reinforced composites better interfacial properties than other thermoplastics such as Polypropylene and Nylon 6,6. As K is concerned, same order values are obtained for PEEK and Polypropylene.

	GPEEK30	CPEEK30
$\epsilon = 1.0 \%$	23	31
$\epsilon = 1.5 \%$	42	47
$\epsilon = 2.0 \%$	75	82
ϵ_{break}	102	131

Table 3. Critical fibre length, L_c (μm), at several strains in the non linear part of stress-strain curve.

	τ (MPa)	K
GPEEK30	80	0.57
CPEEK30	202	0.93
Nylon 6,6/GF (Wf = 30%) ⁵	45	-
Polypropylene/GF (Wf = 30%) ⁷	17.6	0.19
Nylon 6,6/CF (Wf = 30%) ¹⁰	130	-

Table 4. Shear stress values (τ) and the K proportionality constant at break strain for several SFRT.

5.3.- Ultrasonic Young Moduli Determination

Figure 4 shows the Young Moduli of PEEK/CF system in the three material directions defined in Figure 2. E3 and E2, the Young Moduli in the longitudinal and transverse directions of the tensile specimen give nearly the same values at all fibre contents. On the other hand, E1, the modulus in the depth direction is lower. These results are interpreted as a preferential alignment of fibres in the plane 2-3. In the part of the specimen where measurements have been carried out is as if SFRT behaved like a quadratic composite. This type of configuration can also be inferred from similar tendencies found in PEEK/GF system.

Figure 4. Ultrasonic Young Moduli of PEEK/CF in 3 material directions (see Fig. 2).

The comparison of ultrasonic and tensile results is not an easy task. Since different geometries acting to the melt filling process are implicated, the state of orientation of fibres in central parts of the specimens submitted to tensile test and in shoulders submitted to ultrasonic tests, must not be similar. As shown by Crowson¹¹ a higher degree of alignment is expected in parts involved in convergent melting flow processes than in those of divergent flows. In consequence higher fibre alignment is expected in tensile than in ultrasonic tested parts. In contrast, in viscoelastic polymeric materials, their elastic response is favoured at short testing times. Since higher speeds are involved in ultrasonic measurements, Young Moduli obtained by this method are usually higher than those obtained by tensile tests. PEEK matrix results (see table 5) confirm this fact, being the ultrasonic value 31% higher than its corresponding tensile value. The comparison of results in composites should reflect these considerations.

	E3t(GPa)	E3u(GPa)
PEEK	3.10±.04	4.11±.47
GPEEK10	4.70±.42	5.45±.59
GPEEK20	5.98±.82	6.71±1.27
GPEEK30	7.44±.35	8.11±1.37
CPEEK10	6.37±.49	6.62±1.3
CPEEK20	9.34±.52	9.50±.83
CPEEK30	12.38±.77	11.02±.66

Table 5. Young Modulus in the mold filling direction by tensile (E3t)and ultrasonic (E3u) tests.

Comparing Young Moduli of composites in the mold filling direction by ultrasonic and tensile measurements, higher E₃ values are generally found both in carbon and glass reinforced systems by ultrasonic results (CPEEK30 is the only one giving higher modulus by tensile). Quantitatively, however, the differences obtained in the case of composites are not as high as those found in the matrix. This is a clear demonstration of the higher orientation of fibres in tensile parts than in ultrasonic parts. Moreover the E(ultrasonic)/E(tensile) ratio is higher for PEEK/GF than in PEEK/CF systems at all fibre contents. At this point, several remarks could be made. First, the fibre volume content is higher in PEEK/CF systems. Second, these results might be interpreted as higher alignment of CF than GF in PEEK melting convergent flows, or higher alignment of the later in divergent flows or as a combination of both effects at the same time. Finally, the E(ultrasonic)/E(tensile) ratio decreases with increasing fibre content in both composite systems as expected from the lower content of the viscoelastic component in the composite.

6.- CONCLUSIONS

Kelly-Tyson model, when it is applied to predict the stress-strain behavior of short carbon reinforced PEEK gives higher fibre-matrix shear strength and higher critical length values than when it is employed with short glass fibre PEEK composites. In the context offered by this theory it has also been found that PEEK offers to fibres better interfacial properties than other thermoplastics.

The interest of a non destructive ultrasonic technique for mechanical characterization of SFRT has been evaluated by means of a comparative study of Young Modulus of composites obtained by ultrasonic and tensile measurements. It is demonstrated that if effects such as the viscoelastic nature of the matrix, and the complex processing-microstructure relationships of SFRT are considered, the tensile and ultrasonic results are compatible.

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